

TLC of some cations and their separation by naturally occurring mixed oxides impregnated plates

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Some cations have been separated from their binary mixture using TLC plates impregnated by naturally occurring mixed oxides.

Combined ion exchange and solvent extraction technique (C.I.E.S.E.) has been utilised for the separation of different metal ions using synthetic organic ion exchange papers¹ and inorganic ion exchanger².

This paper reports the easy and effective separation of some metal ions on naturally occurring mixed oxide impregnated plates using C.I.E.S.E. technique and the results are compared with silica gel coated plates under identical conditions. The naturally occurring mixed oxide has

both cation and anion exchange property.

Results and Discussion

R_T , R_L , R_F values for cation in different solvent systems are shown in Table 1. On the basis of these values of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^I, Cr^{III}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and Pb^{II} in different solvent systems, metal ions have been separated from their binary mixtures. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 1

Cation	HCl (2 M) : C ₂ H ₅ OH : H ₂ O (1 : 1 : 1 v/v)		HCl (4 M) : C ₂ H ₅ OH (4 : 1 v/v)		HCl (2 M) : Isoamyl Alcohol (4 : 1 v/v)	
	Si-gel + exchanger (R_T-R_L) R_F	Si-gel (R_T-R_L) R_F	Si-gel + exchanger (R_T-R_L) R_F	Si-gel (R_T-R_L) R_F	Si-gel + exchanger (R_T-R_L) R_F	Si-gel (R_T-R_L) R_F
Cu ^{II}	(0.88-1.00) 0.94	(0.82-0.90) 0.86	(0.55-0.75) 0.65	(0.94-1.00) 0.97	(0.26-0.90) 0.58	(0.69-0.81) 0.75
Ni ^{II}	(0.94-1.00) 0.97	(0.83-0.89) 0.86	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.67-0.83) 0.75	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.65-0.69) 0.67
Co ^{II}	(0.82-1.00) 0.91	(0.78-0.82) 0.80	(0.45-0.55) 0.50	(0.96-1.00) 0.98	(0.00-0.74) 0.37	(0.60-0.79) 0.69
Cd ^{II}	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.96-1.00) 0.98	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.94-0.98) 0.96	(0.10-0.39) 0.24	(0.60-0.64) 0.62
Hg ^I	(0.92-1.00) 0.96	(0.90-1.00) 0.95	(0.13-0.29) 0.21	(0.63-0.69) 0.66	(0.48-0.90) 0.69	(0.83-1.00) 0.92
Cr ^{III}	(0.00-0.92) 0.46	(0.67-0.95) 0.81	(0.50-0.60) 0.55	(0.87-0.96) 0.91	(0.00-1.00) 0.50	(0.25-0.64) 0.44
Zn ^{II}	(0.92-1.00) 0.96	(0.70-0.88) 0.79	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.25-0.43) 0.34
Mn ^{II}	(0.90-0.96) 0.93	(0.52-1.00) 0.76	(0.51-0.61) 0.56	(0.24-0.32) 0.28	(0.29-0.35) 0.32	(0.37-0.43) 0.40
Fe ^{II}	(0.73-0.93) 0.83	(0.00-1.00) 0.50	(0.55-0.75) 0.65	(0.90-1.00) 0.95	(0.00-0.70) 0.35	(0.62-0.82) 0.72
Fe ^{III}	(0.77-0.82) 0.79	(0.80-0.88) 0.84	(0.80-0.90) 0.85	(0.96-1.00) 0.98	(0.00-0.70) 0.35	(0.84-1.00) 0.92
Pb ^{II}	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00	(0.00-0.00) 0.00

Table 2. $(R_T - R_L)R_F$ values of different cations on TLC plates coated with natural inorganic ion exchanger and with silica gel only in different solvent system at $15 \pm 0.5^\circ$

Solvent system	$(R_T - R_L)R_F$		
	Natural ion exchanger	Si-gel	
(1) HCl (2 M) : C ₂ H ₅ OH : H ₂ O (1 : 1 : 1 v/v)	(a) Cu (0.86-1.00)0.93	(0.84-0.90)0.87	
	Cd (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.96-1.00)0.98	
	(b) Hg (0.92-1.00)0.96	(0.90-1.00)0.95	
	Cd (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.96-1.00)0.98	
	(c) Zn (0.92-1.00)0.96	(0.70-0.88)0.79	
	Fe ^{III} (0.76-0.80)0.78	(0.80-0.88)0.84	
	(d) Mn (0.90-0.96)0.93	(0.52-1.00)0.76	
	Fe ^{II} (0.76-0.80)0.78	(0.80-0.88)0.84	
	(2) HCl (4M) : C ₂ H ₅ OH : (4:1, v/v)	(a) Co (0.45-0.55)0.50	(0.96-1.00)0.98
		Ni (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.68-0.84)0.76
(b) Mn (0.51-0.61)0.56		(0.24-0.32)0.28	
Ni (0.00-0.00)0.00		(0.68-0.84)0.76	
(c) Cr (0.50-0.60)0.55		(0.87-0.96)0.91	
Cd (0.00-0.00)0.00		(0.94-0.98)0.96	
(d) Fe ^{II} (0.55-0.75)0.65		(0.90-1.00)0.95	
Cd (0.00-0.00)0.00		(0.94-0.98)0.96	
(e) Cu (0.55-0.75)0.65		(0.94-1.00)0.97	
Hg (0.13-0.29)0.21		(0.63-0.69)0.66	
(3) HCl (2 M) : Isoamyl Alcohol (4 : 1, v/v)	(a) Cu (0.26-0.90)0.58	(0.69-0.81)0.65	
	Ni (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.64-0.68)0.66	
	(b) Hg (0.46-0.92)0.69	(0.83-1.00)0.92	
	Ni (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.64-0.68)0.66	
	(c) Hg (0.48-0.92)0.70	(0.83-1.00)0.90	
	Zn (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.24-0.44)0.34	
	(d) Mn (0.29-0.35)0.32	(0.37-0.43)0.40	
	Zn (0.00-0.00)0.00	(0.25-0.43)0.34	

Glass plates (20 × 20 cm²) were coated (0.2 mm thickness) with a slurry of silica gel and naturally occurring mixed oxide (1:2 by wt.). A set of similarly coated glass plates

were prepared with a slurry of only silica gel for comparison. Solutions of ions were spotted on the plates and after development for 1h, the solvent front was immediately marked and position of different ions were detected using spraying reagents. Various solvent systems were examined for developing chromatogram.

Cadmium is selectively separated from Cu and Hg from their binary mixture. Fe^{III} is selectively separated from Zn and Mn from their binary mixture, using exchanger coated plate and solvent HCl (2 M) : C₂H₅OH : H₂O (1 : 1 : 1, v/v/v).

Nickel is selectively separated from Co and Mn from their binary mixture. Cd is selectively separated from Cr and Fe^{II} from their binary mixture. Hg is selectively separated from Cu and Cr from their binary mixture using exchanger coated plate and solvent HCl (4 M) : C₂H₅OH (4 : 1, v/v).

Nickel is selectively separated from Cu and Hg from their binary mixture. Zn is selectively separated from Hg and Mn from their binary mixture, using exchanger coated plate and solvent HCl (2 M) : isoamyl alcohol (4 : 1, v/v).

In some cases no separation were observed with glass plates coated with silica gel only, whereas the separation was sharp in plates coated with naturally occurring mixed oxide exchanger. Another notable observation was that in ordinary plates, trailing was observed, which was absent in the exchanger coated plates.

References

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